

Ethnopharmacol. 2019 Oct 5;242:112043. doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2019.112043. Epub 2019 Jun 25. PMID: 31252092.

2. El Menyiy N, Guaouguaou FE, El Baaboua A, El Omari N, Taha D, Salhi N, Shariati MA, Aanniz T, Benali T, Zengin G, El-Shazly M, Chamkhi I, Bouyahya A. Phytochemical properties, biological activities and medicinal use of *Centaurium erythraea* Rafn. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2021 Aug 10;276:114171. doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2021.114171. Epub 2021 Apr 30. PMID: 33940085.

3. Determinant of higher plants of Ukraine. - K.: Nauk, Dumka, 1987. - P. 267.

4. Gubergits A.Ya., Solomchenko N.Y. Medicinal plants of Donbass. - Donetsk: Donbass, 1968. - P. 163-165.

5. D.S. Ivashin, Z.F. Katina, I.Z. Rybachuk and others. Reference book on preparations of medicinal plants. - K.: Urozhaj, 1983. - P. 114.

6. Myakushko T.Ya., Zinchenko T.V. Determinant of medicinal plants of Ukraine. - K.: Nauk, Dumka, 1982. - P. 79.

7. Zubtsova I.V., Sklyar V.G. Morphological features of plants and size structure of *centaurium erythraea* coenopopulations on floodplain meadows of the Krolevets-Glukhiv geobotanical district.

ANALYSIS OF BLOOD LIPID SPECTRUM INDICATORS IN CHRONIC PANCREATITIS COMBINED WITH HYPOTHYROIDISM

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Abstract

The study discusses futures of the plasma lipid profile (total cholesterol, triglycerides, low density lipoproteins, high density lipoproteins) and the peculiarities of their changes dynamic's in patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism comorbidity. The study of these pathologies comorbidity is rather promising area of clinical gastroenterology and endocrinology. Study revealed the most pronounced signs of dyslipidaemia in the group of patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism. It confirms close pathogenetic relationship between these pathologies and requires further correction of treatment. Results indicates more comprehensive study of the course and interactions of these diseases in order to avoid complications and disability are needed.

Keywords: chronic pancreatitis, hypothyroidism, total cholesterol, triglycerides, low density lipoproteins, high density lipoproteins.

Introduction

Despite numerous studies, diseases of the pancreas, as a rule, are difficult to diagnose and treat. Nowadays, the mortality from acute pancreatitis remains high, the diagnosis of chronic pancreatitis in the early stages is a special test for the doctor, and its treatment is very often unsuccessful.[1] After all, for many years the pancreas has remained a mysterious and incomprehensible organ for doctors of various specialties: therapists, gastroenterologists, surgeons, oncologists, geneticists, etc.[2]

According to existing modern data, the function of the pancreas is under the influence of a whole series of hormones, and thyroid hormones occupy a special, regulatory place in this series. Thyroid hormones have a multifaceted effect on the body, influencing all organ systems and metabolism as a whole [3]. Deficiency of thyroid hormones leads to disorders on the part of organs and systems - cardiovascular, respiratory, digestive organs, etc. The state of the pancreas in hypothyroidism remains the least studied in gastroenterology,

although B.L. Baker and E.S. Pliske in 1957 pointed out that when the thyroid gland is removed, atrophy of the pancreas is observed, and the use of thyroid hormones leads to the restoration of its mass and structure.

The pancreas is a fairly active and powerful regulator of many biological reactions in the body, so any pathological and even functional changes in it always lead to varying degrees of severity of metabolic disorders. Changes in lipid metabolism, regardless of the underlying disease, are quite often associated with the so-called lipid triad: an increase in the level of triglycerides (TG), atherogenic low-density lipoproteins (LDL), and a decrease in high-density lipoproteins (HDL). This triad underlies the pathogenesis of many diseases and oxidative stress in general. [4]

Among the most frequent complications of hypothyroidism are also dyslipidemias, which are observed in most patients and lead to an increased risk of early development of atherosclerosis. Mechanisms of development of dyslipidemia in chronic pancreatitis and hy-

pothyroidism are considered to be a number of biochemical changes: violation of the structure of total cholesterol (C); a decrease in the activity of cholesterol ester transport protein and hepatic lipase, which provide approximately 30% of the reverse transport of cholesterol; violation of the structure of high-density lipoproteins (HDL), which leads to a violation of the reverse transport of cholesterol; decrease in the number and sensitivity of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) receptors in the liver, which cause a decrease in hepatic excretion of cholesterol and subsequently increase the levels of LDL and very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL); as well as impaired renal glomerular function (decreased glomerular filtration rate) and slowing of LDL clearance.

Lipid disorders in patients with CP and hypothyroidism

Index	Patients with chronic pancreatitis (group No. 1)	Patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism (group No.2)	Practically healthy persons (group No. 3)
Total cholesterol (mmol/l)	5,3±0,17	6,28±0,09	3,44±0,17
Triglycerides (mmol/l)	167±0,18	266±0,43	130,39±0,19
Low-density lipoprotein (mmol/l)	2,5±0,27	3,56±0,21	1,95±0,37
High density lipoproteins (mmol/l)	1,23±0,14	1,11±0,06	1,41±0,06

Research results Manifestations of dyslipidemia were observed in patient groups No. 1 and No. 2. However, they were more pronounced in patients of the 3rd group (with combined pathology), which turned out to be the highest among all compared groups: indicators of total cholesterol increased by 1.82 times ($p<0.05$), LDL cholesterol increased by 80.7% ($p<0.05$) and TG by 2 times ($p<0.05$) and a decrease in HDL by 18.9% ($p<0.05$) compared to practically healthy individual

Conclusion. A significant difference in the indicators of cholesterol, LDL and TG was noted in patients of the 2nd group compared to the individuals of the 1st group. Thus, the most pronounced signs of dyslipidemia were found in patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism, which confirms the close pathogenetic connection between such nosologies, a marker of thyroid insufficiency (increased TSH level, decreased T3 and T4), manifestations of dyslipidemia, and damage to the pancreas. The study of the comorbidity of these nosologies is a rather promising area of

The aim of the study was to identify pathogenetic features of changes in blood lipid spectrum indicators in patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism.

Materials and methods. To achieve the goal, 83 patients were examined using modern biochemical and instrumental research methods: 33 patients with chronic pancreatitis – group No. 1, 35 patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism – group No. 2, 15 patients were practically healthy individuals included in the group No. 3;

Lipid metabolism was determined using a biochemical selective automated analyzer “KONELAB 20i”. Biochemical study of lipids included determining concentrations of cholesterol, TG, LDL, and HDL.

clinical gastroenterology and endocrinology. The results prove the need for a more detailed study of the course and interaction of these diseases in order to avoid complications and disability.

References

1. Testoni P. A., Mariani A., Arcidiacono P. G. Acute and chronic pancreatitis. - Turin: Edizioni Minerva Medica. - 2013. - 193 p
2. Gubergryts N.B. Chronic pancreatitis: work on mistakes /N. V. Belyaeva, A. E. Klochkov, P. G. Fomenko. Modern gastroenterology. - 2015. - No. 3(83). - P. 98-104.
3. Prystupyuk O.M. Hypothyroidism: damage to organs and systems. – International journal of endocrinology.–2011.–№4(36)
4. L.S. Babinets, L.M. Migenko. – Violations of lipid metabolism in the pathogenesis of chronic pancreatitis, approaches to their correction.– Newspaper "News of medicine and pharmacy" gastroenterology.– 2011.– No. 382 (thematic number)